

Perceived Behavioural Control and Subjective Norms for Risky Sexual Behaviour Among Adolescents in Ogun State

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Abstract

The study examined perceived behavioural control and subjective norms for risky sexual behaviour among adolescents in Ogun State. This study specifically determined the subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour among adolescents; assessed the perceived behavioral control against risky sexual behaviour; examined the relationship between subjective norms and practice of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents; and determined the relationship between the perceived behavioural control of risky sexual behaviour and the practice. A descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted in this study. The study was carried out among senior secondary school students in one Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The sample size of 384 was calculated using Cochran's formula while the sample size was selected using multistage sampling procedure. The research instrument was self-designed by the researcher using information obtained from literatures on subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour, perceived behavioral control against risky sexual behaviour and practice of risky sexual behaviour. The face and content validity of the instrument was established by experts in the field of adolescents' sexual and reproductive health. Test re-test method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument with reliability coefficient of 0.813. This shows that the instrument was reliable and appropriate for the study. The findings of the study revealed that respondents' subjective norms of risky sexual behaviour by adolescents was good while the knowledge of perceived behavioural control against risky sexual behaviour of the respondents was also

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adequate. It was recommended that adolescents should be educated on the consequences of unsafe sexual acts at their age.

Keywords: Adolescents, Behavioural Control, Subjective Norms, Risky Sexual Behaviour,

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Introduction

The importance of healthy sexual awareness and development among adolescents for their future health status cannot be overemphasized (Alemán-Díaz, et al, 2018). Healthy sexual development contributes significantly to the holistic personal well-being of the adolescents but when they become unaware of this, they will develop different risky sexual behaviors. Sexual behavior encompasses all activities which gratify an individual's sexual needs. Sexual behaviors have been studied in different contexts such as sexual practices, sexual relationships, reproductive health, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), and contraception. Though sexual behavior and expression of sexuality are normal phenomena, the context in which sexual behavior is expressed determines if the behavior is abnormal or risky (Chawla & Sarkar, 2019). There are different types of risky sexual behaviour which include premarital sex, abortion and multiple sex partners among adolescents.

Several studies have revealed that adolescents are at high risk of developing risky sexual behavior. According to Behulu, et al (2019), premarital sex is the most commonly practice risky sexual behaviour among adolescents. It involves penetrative vaginal intercourse performed between teenagers before formal marriage. Shahid and Wahab (2017) explained premarital sex as voluntary sexual intercourse between unmarried persons which is increasing worldwide. The world population of adolescents is estimated to be 1.2 billion while 85% live in developing countries (Salih, et al, 2015). Regassa, Chala and Adeba (2016) reported that 29% and 23% of boys and girls respectively have premarital sex during adolescence period. Meanwhile, many studies carried out in sub-Saharan Africa have shown high and increasing premarital sexual activities among adolescents (Teferra, Erena & Kebede, 2015). Studies have documented that early sexual initiators were more likely to report undesired consequences of sexual initiation such as teenage motherhood and sexually transmitted infections (STIs).

There is a link between the intention to perform behaviour and the actual performance of the behaviour (Davison, McLaughlin & Giles, 2019). It is important to identify adolescents who have the intention to engage in risky sexual behaviour as they are likely to perform the actual behaviour if the external conditions are favourable. They can then be included in interventions to promote safe sexual behaviour which can have positive impact on them. It is assumed that adolescents with good knowledge about sexually transmitted infection (STIs) and its prevention will not have intention of engaging in risky sexual behaviour (Crocker, et al, 2019).

Subjective norms among adolescents are referred to as behaviours expected or supported by people around them, such as family, peers, and colleagues (Fang, et al, 2017). Subjective norms are thoughts reflecting perceived social pressure from important personalities (parents and friends) to perform a behavior, which is majorly affected by one's motivation to comply with those behaviours.

Mengistie, et al (2015) found out that subjective norm exhibits a positive influence on a particular behaviour as well as has a significant influence in motivating adolescent toward risky sexual behavior. Behaviour is always influenced by three factors which are the individual's attitude, the influence of social factors (subjective norm) and perceived behavioural control. The perceived behavioral control and subjective norms of adolescents may have significant influenced on practice of risky sexual behavior.

Thus, the study examined perceived behavioural control and subjective norms for risky sexual behaviour among adolescents in Ogun State. This study specifically:

1. determined the subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour among adolescents;

2. assessed the perceived behavioral control against risky sexual behaviour;
3. examined the relationship between subjective norms and practice of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents; and
4. determined the relationship between the perceived behavioural control of risky sexual behaviour and the practice

Research Questions

The study provided answers to the following questions:

1. What are the subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour among adolescents?
2. What are perceived behavioral control against risky sexual behaviour?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for this study.

1. There is no significant relationship between subjective norms and practice of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents.
2. There is no significant relationship between the perceived behavioural control of risky sexual behaviour and the practice.

Methodology

A descriptive cross sectional survey design was adopted in this study. The study was carried out among senior secondary school students in one Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The sample size of 384 was calculated using Cochran's formula while the sample size was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

The research instrument was self-designed by the researcher using information obtained from literatures on subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour, perceived behavioral control against risky sexual behaviour and practice of risky sexual behaviour. The face and content validity of the instrument was established by experts in the field of adolescents' sexual and reproductive health. Test re-test method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument by pre-testing it among forty (40) students in a similar population group. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Statistics was used to analysed the data collected which yielded reliability coefficient of 0.813. This shows that the instrument was reliable and appropriate for the study.

Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage was calculated from the data collected for this study. Chi-square was used to analyse the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: The socio-demographic information of the respondents

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	186	48.1
	Female	201	51.9
	Total	387	100.0
Age	13-15	144	37.2
	16-19	243	62.8
	Total	387	100.0
Class	SSS1	134	34.6
	SSS2	133	34.4
	SSS3	120	31.0
	Total	387	100.0
Religion	Christianity	245	63.3

	Islam	127	32.8
	Traditional	13	3.4
	Others	2	0.5
	Total	387	100.0
Ethnic group	Yoruba	323	83.5
	Hausa	26	6.7
	Igbo	35	9.0
	Others	3	0.8
	Total	387	100.0

Source: *Field survey, 2021*

The table 1 shows the Socio-demographic information of the respondents. The study showed that 186 (37.0%) of the respondents were male and the females were 201 (51.9%) while 144 (37.2%) of the respondents were in the age group 13-15 years, 243 (62.8%) were in the group 16-19 years with a mean age of 17.2 years. The class distribution of the respondents was SSS1, SSS2 and SSS3 and 134 (34.6%), 133 (34.4%) and 120 (31.0%) were in the classes respectively. The table also shows the religious distribution of the respondents, 245 (63.3%) practice Christianity, 127 (32.8%) practice Islam, while 13 (3.4%) of them were traditional worshippers and 2 (0.5%) practiced other religion. Also, 323 (83.5%) of the respondents were Yoruba, 35 (9.0%) of them were Igbo, while 26 (6.7%) of them were Hausa while 3 (0.8%) were of other ethnic groups.

Research Question 1: What are the subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour among adolescents?

Table 2: The summary of the respondents' subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour

Subjective norms level	Category of scores	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Negative	0-5	89	23.0%
Positive	6-13	298	77.0%
Total		387	100

Source: *Field survey, 2021*

Figure i: Bar chart showing respondents’ subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour

Respondents were asked 13 questions to assess their subjective norms on risky sexual behaviour. The level of subjective norms of respondents was shown by giving a score of 1 to respondents who had positive norms to the statement and 0 to respondents who had negative norms to the statements. The scores were categorized into the following:

Negative norms- respondents who score between 0-5

Positive norms -respondents who score between 6-13

Table 2 shows the subjective norms of the respondents towards risky sexual behavior. Here, that majority of the respondents 298 (77.0%) had positive subjective norms about risky sexual behaviour while 89 (23.0%) had negative subjective norms about risky sexual behaviour.

Research Question 2: What are perceived behavioral control against risky sexual behaviour?

Table 3: The summary of the respondents’ perceived control against risky sexual behaviour

Level of perceived control	Category of scores	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Negative	0-6	68	17.6%
Positive	7-14	319	82.4%
Total		387	100

Source: *Field survey, 2021*

Respondents were asked 14 questions to assess their perceived control against risky sexual behaviour. The level of perceived control of respondents against risky sexual behaviour was shown by giving a score of 1 to respondents who had positive perceived control to the statement and 0 to respondents who had negative perceived control to the statements. The scores were categorized into the following:

- Negative perceived control- respondents who score between 0-6
- Positive perceived control -respondents who score between 7-14

Table 3 shows the perceived behavioural control of the respondents towards risky sexual behavior. Here, that majority of the respondents 319 (82.4%) had positive perceived control against risky sexual behaviour while 68 (17.6%) had negative perceived control about risky sexual behavior.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between subjective norms and practice of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents.

Table 4: Relationship between subjective norms and practice of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents

	Value	df	p-value
Pearson Chi-Square	10.459	2	0.005
Likelihood Ratio	10.154	2	
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.562	1	
Spearman correlation			0.142

The hypothesis testing in the table below shows that the Chi-square (χ^2) and the p-value. The p-value of 0.005 was recorded for the hypothesis of respondents which is less than the alpha (α) p-value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H₁) is accepted. This shows that there is significant relationship between subjective norms and practice of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents. Also, there is a

positive correlation between the subjective norms and practice of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents (0.142).

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the perceived behavioural control of risky sexual behaviour and the practice.

Table 5: Relationship attitude towards risky sexual behaviour and perceived behavioral control

	Value	df	p-value
Pearson Chi-Square	1.731	2	0.421
Likelihood Ratio	1.882	2	
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.008	1	
Spearman correlation			-0.005

The hypothesis testing in the table below shows that the Chi-square (χ^2) and the p-value. The p-value of 0.421 was recorded for the hypothesis of respondents which is greater than the alpha (α) p-value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis (H₀) is accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H₁) is rejected. This shows that there is no significant relationship between the perceived behavioural control of risky sexual behaviour and the practice of risky sexual behaviour. Also, there is a negative correlation between the perceived behavioural control of risky sexual behaviour and the practice of risky sexual behaviour (-0.005).

Discussion

Attaining the adolescent age comes with issues that must be addressed as this stage has implications on the reproductive and sexual health of the individual (Duru *et.al.*, 2010). This study shows the mean age of the respondents was 17.2 ± 2.1 years and this is similar to the study carried out by Baudouin, Wongsawat and Sudnongbua (2020) where the mean age of the participants was 16.5 years. In this study, more than half of the participants were females which is in comparison with the works of Famutimi and Oluwatoyin (2014). Also, most of the respondent were Yoruba, this support the findings of Babatunde *et al.* (2014) and Asekun-Olarinmoye & Oladele (2009) that reported more Yorubas in the study which could have been due to the fact that the study was carried out in a Yoruba dominating region. The majority of the participants in this study were Christians and this was supported by the findings of Daba (2016).

In this study, 77.0% of the participants have a positive subjective norms and values about risky sexual behaviour. Previous studies have shown that family norms and religion influence sexual behaviour among the adolescents (Faimau *et al.*, 2016). Here, 23.0% of the respondents have negative subjective norms about risky sexual behaviour and this was also reported by Wusu *et al.* (2014).

A large number 82.4% of the sampled adolescents in this study had a generally high positive view towards the perceived behavioural control against risky sexual behaviour. This is consistent with the findings of Mkumbo (2013) and in contrast with that Faimau *et al.* (2016) who found that the respondents have a low behavioural control against risky sexual behaviours.

The study revealed that there was significant relationship between subjective norms and practice of risky sexual behaviour among adolescents in this study. Espada *et al* (2016)

and Espada et al (2012) reported that individuals with positive subjective norms were less likely to engage in risky sexual behaviour and this was consistent with the findings of this study. As found in this study, Omoyeni, Akanni and Fatusi (2014) also reported a relationship between high subjective norms and the practice of risky sexual behaviours where these acts were engaged in by the adolescents for fun and nonchalant disposition to the dangers of risky sexual acts. Positive subjective norms such as parental communication and religion have been found to have significant relationships with the practice of risky sexual behaviour (Faimua et al., 2006) and this is in line with the findings of this study. Also, societal norms as subjective norms have significant relationship on safe sex practice (Musizvingoza, 2015) and it is in line with this study.

This study also shows that there was no significant relationship between the perceived behavioural control of risky sexual behaviour and the practice among the respondents and Odeigah et.al. (2019) reported a similar finding in a study that the participants have a poor behavioural culture towards the practice of risky sexual behaviour. The result of this study also agreed with the reports of Fako et al., (2010) and Mkumbo (2013) that showed no significant relationship between the practice of risky sexual behaviour and the perceived behavioural control. However, this did not support the findings of Faimau et al. (2016) who reported that the participants' practice of risky sexual behaviour and the behavioural control.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the respondents' subjective norms of risky sexual behaviour by adolescents was good while the knowledge of perceived behavioural control against risky sexual behaviour of the respondents was also adequate. It was recommended that adolescents should be educated on the consequences of unsafe sexual acts at their age.

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